

Couples Challenges and Negative Impacts of Social Media on Christian Marriages in Nigeria

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Abstract

Marriage is an old institution which has been at the core of man's social life from creation. In the Old Testament, the origin of marriage is traceable to God in Genesis Chapters 1 and 2. Jesus also endorsed the institution of marriage in the New Testament by providing wine for the wedding at Cana in Galilee (Jhn.2). In Christianity, marriage is a covenant in which one is not expected to jump in and jump out. Aside some couples challenges which often lead to conflict or divorce, social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and many more have also contributed negatively to this problem in Nigeria. The objective of this paper therefore, is to examine some of the challenges and the negative impact of social media in Christian marriages with a view to providing some solutions. The paper adopted historical and descriptive methods coupled with internet search and interview of some church leaders. The findings reveal that common among couple's challenges in Nigeria are individual differences, childlessness and unemployment. Also, aside the fact that social media made it simpler for people to stay in touch, get information, learn new things, share ideals and even spread the gospel, its excessive use in Christian homes can lead to increased marital conflict, decrease marital satisfaction and separation or divorce. To solve some of these problems, the need to understand God's purpose for marriage and other essentials in husband and wife relationship has to be emphasized. The paper recommended that not only should Christian couples be mindful of how they use social media chats at home, they should also comply with the Biblical teachings of loving, trusting and embracing commitment to their marriage. In conclusion, husband and wife in Christian homes are required to guide their eyes and heart against the temptations and distractions that social media can present to them.

Keywords: Social Media, Christian Home, Husband and Wife, Biblical Teachings

Introduction

Marriage is the first institution that ever was. It is as old as human history, and this sacred ordinance has its basis in Genesis 18:25. It is, therefore, defined as the relationship between a man and woman who had made a legal agreement to live together for life. It is the foundation on which the lives and relationship of family members are initiated or built. In the rite of passage of life, namely birth, marriage and death, it is the marriage ceremony that humans can personally witness on earth. Ogedengbe says that "In most cultures and religions, especially in Nigeria, neither the man nor woman is considered important in the society after reaching maturity, without a spouse."¹ In his own submission, Oderinde avers that "marriage is a social obligation which everybody in a few cases is expected to fulfill as part of his or her divine origin from God."² In the Genesis account of the creation, the origin of marriage is recorded in the first two chapters. The first account in Genesis 1: 26 – 30 says that God created male and female, with the sole aim of having mutual fellowship, after He had created other creatures. The second account in Genesis 2: 18 – 25 states that God first created man before He later saw the need for a helpmeet for the man. Consequently, the first woman emerged. Then the man said "This is the bone of my bone and the flesh of my flesh. She shall be called woman, because she was taken out of man" (Gen. 2: 23).

According to the *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*, marriage “ as a legally and socially sanctioned union between one or more husbands and one or more wives that accord status to their offspring and is regulated by laws, rules, customs, beliefs and attitudes that prescribe the rights and duties of the partners.”³ Douglas opines that God was the available eye- witness, when Adam and Eve accepted each other as husband and wife. The marriage contracted in Eden was between a man and his woman, which by implication was monogamous. Since then marriage has become a social obligation for every man to leave his father and mother and cleave to his wife and the two becomes one.⁴ Christians believe that marriage is a gift from God, which should not be taken for granted.

The three major religions recognized in Nigeria are African Traditional Religion, Islam and Christianity. While the first two can marry more than one wives, marriage in Christianity is meant to be between one man and one woman (Matt. 19:4-6) which is monogamy. Notwithstanding, there are some Christians with more than one wives are referred to as polygamists. Marriage is a covenant relationship between two imperfect people coming together to love each other unconditionally. Christians are not expected to go into marriage with the aim of experimentation; divorce, separation and re-marriage. Douglas surmises that Christian marriage was intended to be a permanent one- a life contract. Couples are to remain as one until death do them apart.⁵ Christ Himself stressed on the indissoluble firmness of the nuptial bond when He said that “what God hath joined together, let no man put asunder” (Matt. 19:6); and “every one that puts away his wife and he that marries the put away wife, committed adultery” (Lk.16:18). In the actual sense, the Christian marriage is built on the relationship between Christ and the Church according to Ephesians’ 5:21-25. Therefore, in Christian marriage; divorce or separation is not accepted according to the Scriptures in Matthew.19:1-6. It is, however, unfortunate that aside some couples’ challenges which have been common factors for divorce, many marriages are now breaking down pre-maturely in contemporary society because of social media. This paper sets out to unfold the positive and negative impacts of social media on Christian marriages in Nigeria.

Some Couples Challenges in Nigeria

Marriage in Christianity is supposed to make two become one, united party and strong enough to stand against the devil and his cohorts here on earth. This is the end product of love. “Two are better than one because they have a good reward for their labour (Eccl.4:9). However, many Christian marriages in Nigeria have experienced diverse challenges among which are:

Individual Differences

Crises in marriage are not, of course, inevitable in the early years of marriage. The first challenge is individual differences. According to Johnson Adediran, the husband and wife may have had a long courtship but denied the right to certain things before contracting marriage. Such things are sleeping together and seeing the nakedness of one another. Consequently, problems like snoring, skin blemish, differences in neatness and responses to issues may be a challenge in marriage. In this situation, there is a need for Couples to understand each other. Couples who cannot accommodate and understand one another as a result of individual differences may soon allow for a divorce.⁶ In his own submission, Oyedepo says “Understanding is the act of grappling mentally, comprehending, discerning and interpreting the actions of one another as husband and wife. It is also a determining factor for a peaceful home.”⁷ Husbands and wife must understand that they have different background, approach to issues and temperament. These peculiarities must be studied, understood and appreciated or tolerated to sustain harmonious and peaceful relationship. Husband and wife must not expect perfection from one another in all matters. There is no perfection in marriage because they are humans and only God is perfect.

Interference of Third Party

This is a common problem facing many African homes today, particularly in Nigeria. Many homes in Nigeria usually have the problem of third party interference such as in-laws and friends. Bolarinwa testifies that, just because her husband is from another tribe, it took her much time to cope with the in-laws. They frustrated the marriage with their interference in every issue such as finance, the number of children they should have, the maximum assistance the husband should offer domestically and so on. According to her, that interference affected her marriage so much that at a point, she and her husband had to express their feelings through messages written on pieces of paper. She warned that, on no account should the husband or the wife allow his or her relatives interfere unnecessarily with their marital affairs.⁸ Although, it is a tradition in Africa that relations and in-laws are still considered one big family with couple after marriage, yet their advice should only be heartily welcomed when such would not create problems in the home.

Childlessness

According to Williams, childlessness is one of the devil's greatest strategies for pulling down homes especially in Africa where a childless couple is written off. Childlessness though, is a natural unhappy condition, even for both couples, many would refer to it as a problem caused by either one of the couple particularly the wife. Relations especially the mother of the husband, could go to the extent of finding another wife for her son even when such action is not pleasant to their son.⁹ Childlessness in marriage is often considered as misfortune or failure in Africa. In his submission, Amolo says "it should be understood that procreation is only one of the purposes of marriage and therefore one should not consider his marriage a defeat, if it does not result into having a child."¹⁰

Unemployment and Joblessness

Most marriages have separated because the man could not perform his duties of taking care of the family due to unemployment. Amolo avers that some ladies cannot stand living with a man who cannot provide for her. Unemployment is a demoralising experience, for both men and women in Nigeria. Indeed, unemployment is among the greatest sources of marital stress at the present time. All forms of social deprivation create strained for marriage. As a result of joblessness, newly married couples are sometimes obliged to live with their in-laws, and this increases the strain for couples who need privacy and peace to adjust to each other in the deprived areas. For those who secure accommodation, the payment of rents or mortgages is a recurrent burden and problem. There is exploitation by some landlords in the area of flat-letting. These experiences have not been favourable to some wives and therefore cause separation or divorce.¹¹

The Impacts of Social Media on Christian Marriages

Social media is a digital technology that allows the sharing of ideas and information, including text and visuals, through virtual networks and communities. It refers to the means of interactions among people in which they create, share, and or exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks. The office of communications and marketing manages the main Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and You Tube accounts.¹² Social media started out as a way for people to interact with friends and family but soon expanded to serve many different purposes. In 2004, MySpace was the first network to reach 1million monthly active users. More than 4.7 billion people around the world use social media and the largest platforms worldwide are Face book, You Tube, WhatsApp, Instagram, and WeChat. ¹³ In early 2023, 94.8% of users accessed chat and messaging apps and websites, followed closely by social platforms with 94.6% of users. ¹³

Some Positive Impacts of Social Media on Christian Marriages

It is necessary to recognize that social media, like any other tool, can have positive and negative implications. While certain potential dangers and pitfalls are associated with social media use, there are also many positive ways social media can benefit Christian relationships. For example, couples who share their relationship online by posting pictures and status updates about their partner could develop higher relationship satisfaction. Social media, if used decently, could also positively impact spouses' relationships, possibly by facilitating communication and creating shared online experiences.

Since communication plays a vital role in keeping and boosting the longevity of a marriage, couples can use social media to stay connected and communicate during times of separation, such as during deployment or long-distance relationships; can stand a chance of achieving higher levels of marital satisfaction and lower levels of divorce. Stokel-Walker avers that social media can positively affect Christian marriages and families when used responsibly and with care. By fostering connections and communication and providing opportunities for learning and growth, social media can help strengthen our relationships with our spouses, families, and God. Therefore, as we navigate the double-edged sword of social media, let us seek to use it for good and for the glory of God.¹⁴

In his own submission, Eberendu says that social media can provide opportunities for learning, growth, and spiritual development in relationship. Platforms like YouTube and podcasts offer a wealth of resources for Christian couples seeking to deepen their understanding of the Bible and grow in their faith. Christian bloggers and influencers offer insights and inspiration that can help married couples live out their faith in practical ways. It can also provide valuable resources for seeking knowledge and understanding regarding ways to improve their relationship.¹⁵ According to Opoola, social media can be a powerful tool for sharing and spreading the gospel. Platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok offer opportunities for Christians to share their love stories online and give inspiration to others in new and creative ways. Also, by using hashtags and engaging with others, Couples can reach a wider audience and share the good news of Jesus Christ with people who might not otherwise have encountered it. Jesus Himself spoke to the importance of spreading the gospel, with Matthew 28:19-20 stating, "Go ye therefore and teach all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Ghost; teaching them to observe all things whatsoever I have commanded you; and, lo, I am with you always, even unto the end of the world." With thoughtful and responsible use, social media can be a powerful tool for connection, growth, and positive change.¹⁶

Some Negative Impacts of Social Media on Christian Marriages

While social media can offer many benefits, including increased connectivity and access to information that can help marriage blossom, it can also present many challenges and temptations that undermine the health and stability of relationships between spouses. Some ways social media can negatively impact Christian marriages are:

Wrong Marital Choices

In spite of the fact that marital choices vary from one couple/family to the other, making good and right choices is one of the God-given responsibilities of every human being including the choice of healthy partner to marry. One phenomenon that is influencing people's choices in this modern age is the social media and the internet. In the choice of marriage partner, many have adopted the use of text messages and internets (Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram) to send their photos or videos (phonograph) to one another for the purpose of getting a marriage partner. Stokel-Walker opines that although, it is a truism that social media has enabled many to meet new people

or old contacts, to communicate, share and/or exchange ideas and feelings online or Phones; it is noteworthy, however, that it has also exposed users to negative consequences including marriage. This type of practice is totally unacceptable in Christianity.¹⁷

False Identity and Fake Lives

Many marriage partners via social media and internet (cellphones) are total strangers who may not unfold their real identity. In fact, many people that involved themselves in a relationship via social media live fake lives and deceived people into believing them of the type of person they claim to be. Stokel-Walker maintains that it is a pity that most of the relationships built out of online dating and ends in marriage, do result to frustrations and catastrophes. So many singles are now found wanting for not waiting on the Lord through prayers to get a good marriage partner as being taught in most Pentecostal churches.¹⁸

More Time for Online Chatting Over Attention of the Spouse

Since more time is being devoted to the use of social media these days, couples are having less time to be together. Devotion of more time on online chartings at the neglect of spouse has led to pre-mature breakdown in marital relationship. Eberendu asserts that over use of Social Networking Sites leads to the decline of couple's relationship because even when some couples are in the same room, and at times on the same bed, they may be engrossed in social media neglecting their spouses. This choice to be online or be on social media has affected the communication sphere of many marriages.¹⁹ In fact, a concern has been raised that many couples have had pre-mature separation as a result of spending too much time on these social media sites, creating problems in their family life and making it difficult to maintain good relationships with their spouses.

Hidden Secrets and Deceit

Social media enables wives or husbands to have some secrets which they intentionally hide from one another. Shoremi submits that many couples had issues and extra marital affairs which they hide using codes to deny access to their smart phones or garget. When such secret or lies unfold, it could cause breakdown or pre-mature separation.²⁰ For example, a man who has extra marital affairs with another lady or woman will always deny his spouse access to his phone and vice versa. Again, a wife who has been deceived by her husband through social media that he has cars, buildings, lives in abroad and so on but all discovered to be fake after marriage, such marriage is liable to experience a pre-mature separation. Also, a husband may get information through social media chats that her wife cannot conceive as a result of several abortions or informed that she already has a child for someone in secret and refuse to tell her husband before marriage, this may lead to divorce.

Comparison and Envy

According to Babalola, one of the most common negative impacts of social media on Christian marriages and families is the tendency to compare their lives and relationships to others online, leading to feelings of envy, inadequacy, and discontentment. This is often exacerbated by the highly curreted and idealized images that many people present on social media, which can create unrealistic expectations and standards for others. As the Apostle Paul warns in 2 Corinthians 10:12, "For we dare not make ourselves of the number or compare ourselves with some that commend themselves; but they measuring themselves by themselves, and comparing themselves among themselves, are not wise." Instead, husbands and wives are called to focus on the unique blessings and challenges of their lives and relationships and be content with what God has given them.²¹

Addiction and Distraction

Social media can be highly addictive and distracting, pulling husband or wife away from responsibilities and relationships with each other. In many cases, social media use can become compulsive and interfere with the ability to be present and engaged in daily lives and interactions with loved ones. Ephesians 5:15-16 says, "See then that ye walk circumspectly, not as fools, but as wise, redeeming the time, because the days are evil". As Christians, husbands and wives must be mindful of how they spend their time and prioritize their relationships with spouses and families above social media.

Infidelity and Temptation

Eberendu states that social media can present many opportunities for temptation and infidelity between husband and wife through direct messaging, communication with others, and exposure to sexually explicit or provocative content online. This can erode trust, intimacy, and commitment in Christian marriages and lead to devastating consequences.²² Jesus warns in Matthew 5:28, "But I say unto you, that whosoever looketh on a woman to lust after her hath committed adultery with her already in his heart." Therefore, as Christians, husband and wife must guard their hearts and minds against the temptations and distractions that social media can present and remain faithful and committed to each other.

Conflict and Misunderstanding

Social media can contribute to conflict and misunderstanding in Christian marriages, especially when communication online is not clear, honest, and respectful. In his comment, Eberendu says that misinterpretation, miscommunication, and even cyber bullying can undermine the trust, respect, and love essential to healthy relationships.²³ As Christians, husband and wife must be mindful of the potential negative impacts of social media on their marriages by remaining focused on their relationship with God and family.

Panacea to Couples Challenges and the Menace of Social Media in Christian Marriages **Understanding the Purpose of Christian Marriage**

There are reasons for everything God created. At creation, God did not waste time creating any worthless things but was judicious. Marriage, which was instituted by God, was intended to fulfill certain functions. The success of any Christian marriage in the web of social media therefore, could be determined by a number of factors:

First, it is God's intention that marriage should offer companionship. According to Williams, loneliness has been discovered to be one of the causes of mental retardation and suicide and marriage is therefore an antidote to loneliness.²⁴ After creation, God said it was not good that the man should be alone (Gen 2:18). God, therefore, made the woman for the man, thereby instituting marriage. Ogedengbe says when a husband accepts the fact that the purpose of having a wife is to solve his loneliness, not only is he expected to love the woman but to also appreciate the curiosity of the woman calling or sending messages through social media to know his whereabouts especially when he delays or fails to come home at the expected time.²⁵

For couples' to have a happy home, communication is very important between the husband and the wife. Schoenberg comments that a feature common to many problems in marriage is lack of communication between the couples. With much concentration on online chartings at home rather than communicating with spouse, the transition from the joy, affection and mutual concern in marriage can sometimes be traumatic. In some homes, words are rarely exchanged except in anger, in nagging or in demand. Sometimes social media has caused so much havoc in the home that the main, if not, the sole communication between married couples is through their children. When the children leave home, the couples live in chilly or perhaps frosty silence.²⁶ If it was not good

to be alone for Adam in the Garden of Eden that time, it is even more so today. Marriage therefore, is not for couples to live together as roommates, but to live as best of friends.

Also, it is evident from the scripture that one of the primary purposes of marriage is to provide a helpmeet for man. Ogedengbe opines that before Eve was given to Adam, certain responsibilities had been committed to him. For example, that it was his duty to dress and keep the garden (Gen 2:15). But God saw that he needed help to fulfill these responsibilities. The purpose of God in marriage therefore, is to create a helpmeet that is suitable and complementary; not just any kind of help but a helpmeet in all areas of life. When a wife discovers this truth, she is expected to assist her husband physically and spiritually in all areas of life. For example, as good helpmeet, she must study to know the strong and weak areas of her husband such as finance, decision making, relationship with others and many more. She must be fully committed in ensuring that no other lady outside could do better than her in serving as a helpmeet for her husband.²⁷ Iron sharpeneth iron; the purpose of God in marriage is for a man and his wife to sharpen each other.

Another purpose of marriage according to Oderinde, it is to check sexual impurities. 1 Corinthians 7:2 says “Nevertheless, to avoid fornication, let every man have his own wife, and let every woman have her own husband” Also, Hebrews 13:4a says “Marriage is honourable in all, and the bed undefiled”. So, it is expected that marriage should enable the couples to live a life free from fornication and adultery. Paul further says that, “the wife’s body does not belong to her alone but also to her husband. In the same way, the husband’s body does not belong to him alone but also to his wife” (1 Cor. 7:3;4). Marriage is meant for enjoyment and God has put the sexual urge in both man and woman for maximum enjoyment in marriage.²⁸ Sexual desire is not evil and wicked, rather, it is good and godly but only within the bond of marriage (Gen.2:25, Heb. 13:4). Shoremi warned that couples should not deny each sex as that usually lead to strains in marriage, tension in the home, infidelity and unfaithfulness. During fasting, the only exception to this rule will be the agreement of both husband and wife to restrain from sexual intimacy for a limited time for a specific purpose of giving themselves more completely to prayer and then come together again.²⁹

Again, marriage is for procreation. The human race is being maintained through marriage “And God blessed them, and God said unto them, be fruitful and multiply and replenish the earth, and subdue it” (Gen. 1:28). Here, it is worthy of note that the power to produce after their kind was transferred to the man and the woman. This power can be rightfully exercised only in the context of marriage. On the issue of childlessness, Oyedepo says a partner should not put the blame on the other but be mutually shared. Although, children are the natural results of sexual intercourse between a husband and a wife, they are called “a gift from the Lord”. Sometimes, such childlessness may have spiritual undertone, therefore, apart from medical search for solution by couples, this should be complemented with serious prayers to seek the face of God.³⁰

Understanding some Essential roles in Husband and Wife Relationship

Love

The primary responsibility of husband and wife is to love and trust each other. According to Fawenu, a great burden is placed on the man to love his wife as Christ loves the Church. Ephesians 5:25, 28-29 defines this love beautifully “Husbands, love your wives, even as Christ also love the church and gave himself to it. So, ought men to love their wives as their own bodies. He that loveth his wife loveth himself. For no man ever yet hated his own flesh; but nourished and cherishes it, even as the Lord the church”.³¹ Husbands and wives are to submit to one another (Cor, 3:18, 1 Pet. 3:1-7) It should be noted that women are not inferior nor are they servants in status to the men. However, by marriage covenant, the woman must submit to the husband (Gen. 24:8, 58).

Trust

Trust is an essential ingredient in husbands and wives relationship. The Oxford Advance Dictionary defines trust as the firm belief in the reliability, trust or strength of a person; confident expectation, obligation or responsibility; the state of being relied upon.³² Ogedengbe says ‘Trust is not a gift but a virtue built through experience and over a period of time. No successful family can survive an environment devoid of trust’.³³ One of the virtuous woman aptly painted in Proverbs 31:11 says “The heart of her husband doth safely trust in her, so that he shall have no need of spoil” In building trust, husband and wife must be truthful to one another.

Commitment

Commitment is one of the backbones of any successful relationship, especially Marriage. Genesis 2:24 says “Therefore, shall a man leave his father and his mother, and shall cleave unto his wife: and they shall be one flesh” The interpretation to this is that the man shall be committed to his wife. Oderinde opines that commitment will make husbands and wives choose the expedient above the lawful. That means you forgo some things that take your pleasure in the interest of your marriage.³⁴ Marriage is not a temporary arrangement but a commitment for life. Commitment is the frame work on which a marriage is built. It is expected that a man and his wife be totally committed spiritually, physically and financially. Commitment to the success of marriage makes the husband provide for the home and invest time into the lives of his children. Just as commitment provokes love, it also triggers submission of the wife. Wherever, there is commitment in a marriage, there will be love and submission; both parties working together for the success of their home.

Communication and Prayer

Husband and wife must have time to communicate and pray together frequently. Effective communication and prayer is a major therapy to many problems that may confront the family. It fuels a marriage, keeps love moving to deeper levels and reinforces vital ingredients of trust between couples. A wise man once said, “a family that talks and pray together, stays together.”³⁵

Recommendations

- i. **Do not always be online when your spouse is with you:** It is wrong for a wife or husband to allow social media chats every moment of their relationship. If one is always busy scrolling through time line or news, even at dinner time or while in bed, the other will feel ignored.
- ii. **Avoid Critical Comparison:** There will always be a couple who seems to have better or worse relationship than you. Husband and wife must avoid all comparison to save themselves from the negative effect of social media.
- iii. **Do not look up to your Ex:** No matter how hot or good your ex is, do not lust after his or her timeline. Charting your ex to know how his or her life is, will destroy your marriage if care is not taking. This attitude should be avoided.
- iv. **Be cautious of what and who you like**
Liking and commenting on pictures of handsome men or beautiful women ruined many relationship and marriages. Husbands and wives should be cautious of what they like especially, if it will make their partner jealous or insecure. Be careful not to share things you do not want others to know.

Conclusion

This study has investigated the challenges and negative impact of impact of social media on Christian marriage. The paper shows clearly that in Christianity, marriage is a commitment made by a man and a woman to share their lives together in a permanent and faithful relationship. Marriage in Christianity is “until death do us part” and so, a covenant in which one is not expected to jump in and jump out. The study reveals some of the challenges in Christian marriages in Nigeria which include individual differences, childlessness, and unemployment among others and also provides some antidotes to them. The paper unfold the need for Christian couples to understand the purpose of marriage and their essential roles which includes love, trust, committed to their marriage and pray together.

Also, while there are some positive impacts of social media on Christian marriages, it has been discovered that the negative impacts are more. These negative impacts include fake identity, deceit, comparism and envy, temptation among Christian couples which often lead to conflicts and misunderstanding. The paper recommends that Christian couples must prevent chaos in their homes by being faithful and trusting one another. Finally, it should be noted that divorce is not the perfect will of God in Christian marriages and should not be embraced. Husband and wife in Christian homes are therefore required to guide their eyes and heart against the temptations and distractions that social media can present to them.

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